

A Prelude to Understanding Cognitive Disabilities in School-Age Children

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APA Citation: Singh, H. s/o H.S., Xie, G. H., & Chua, A. C. K. (2022). A prelude to understanding cognitive disabilities in school-age children. *Early Years Research*, 2(2), 1-9.

Abstract

This paper is a prelude to the application of the CHC theory in the assessment and intervention for school-age children with cognitive disabilities (CogDs for short). This is the most common disability type identified by special education officers, school counselors and/or psychologists among school-age children. Cognitive disabilities (also known as intellectual disabilities or IDs for short) is a nebulous term that describes an individual who exhibits more than average difficulty with intellectual tasks. In defining CogDs, there are several overlaps between developmental and cognitive disabilities. These are broad terms used in literature but these labels do not indicate the level of ability or skills. Within the framework of cognition, there are four cognitive subcategories involving what are termed as (i) *lexikos* (ability to use and understand language and literacy skills), (ii) *calculatos* (ability to use and understand mathematics and numeracy skills), (iii) *praxis* (ability to perform voluntary skilled movements), and (iv) *gnosis* (ability to acquire knowledge and its meaning of self and the context in which self engages). In each cognitive category, there are two types of challenging cognitive issues: one is concerned with developmental delay (i.e., dyslexia, dyscalculia, dyspraxia and dysgnosia), and the other is concerned with neurological lesion or injury (i.e., alexia, acalculia, apraxia and agnosia). In this paper, the authors re-examined this framework of cognitive disabilities first proposed by Chia in 2010, and also related each of the four cognitive subcategories to the Cattell-Horn-Carroll (CHC) theory of broad cognitive abilities. **Key Words:** CHC theory, Cognition, Cognitive ability, Cognitive disability, Intellectual disability

Introduction

The term *cognition* is one of the three human behavioral potentials, the other two being affect and conation (Poland, 1974), and as cognitive behavior, “as in the words *recognize* and *recognition*, has to do with intellect, i.e., the use of the mind, whether it is logical or illogical” (Poland, 1974, p. 13). In other words, it refers to the mental or intellectual action or process involved in knowledge acquisition and comprehension through thought, experience, and the senses. This at-birth potential involves the implicit process of thinking (of course, not directly observable), “although an individual human may experience within himself what is called thinking” (Poland, 1974, p. 13). Moreover, cognition encompasses all aspects of intellectual functions and processes which include perception, attention, computation, concept/knowledge formation, decision-making, evaluation (involving analysis and synthesis) and judgment, imagination (also known as fantasizing or sub-creating of all possibilities), intelligence, memory (also working

memory), problem-solving, reasoning, reception and expression of language, and thought. All these cognitive processes use existing knowledge and also to discover new knowledge.

Closely related to cognition is the term *cognitive ability*. According to McGue and Bouchard (1998), cognitive ability constitutes one of the most extensively studied topics within the field of behavioral sciences including genetics and psychology. Cognitive ability is essential for human adaptation and survival, and it is sometimes referred to as general intelligence (g) (Newman & Newman, 2020). It includes the capacity in learning quickly and from experience, planning, problem-solving, reasoning, thinking abstractly, and understanding complex ideas/concepts (Plomin, 1999).

When there is any challenging issue related to cognition, three key terms come into mind: impairment, disability, and handicap, or, in other words, cognitive impairment, cognitive disability,

and cognitive handicap. Do they mean the same thing or they are different from one another?

The often cited definitions of these three terms are provided by the World Health Organization (1980) in *The International Classification of Impairments, Disabilities, and Handicaps* (ICF for short). The term *impairment* refers to any loss or abnormality in terms of psychological, physiological or anatomical structure or function. It affects the functionality of an individual, i.e., the ability to perform a given task or job for which a person is employed to do. Unlike impairment, the term *disability*, on the other hand, refers to any lack, limitation or restriction (that can be the result of an impairment) of one's ability to perform an activity in the manner or within the range considered normal for a typically developed individual. Lastly, the term *handicap* refers to any disadvantage for an individual that causes limitations or prevents the person from fulfilling a role that is typically normal.

When the three terms - impairment, disability and handicap - are used in negative relation to cognitive capability to do a task, cognitive impairment is not the same as cognitive disability and also cognitive handicap should not be taken as synonymous like the other two terms. Cognitive impairment is a more permanent loss or abnormality in an individual's functionality (e.g., memory loss). A good example is when an elderly suffers from a severe form of dementia. Cognitive handicap refers to the mental inability to accomplish something an individual might want to do that most others around him/her are able to accomplish. An example is someone with acquired cognitive handicap (e.g., Broca's or Wernicke's aphasia) due to severe stroke (either ischemic or hemorrhagic) - a medical condition in which poor blood flow to the brain causes necrosis (also known commonly as cell death).

Unlike cognitive impairment or cognitive handicap, the term *cognitive disability* is used when an individual has some specific limitations in his/her mental functions and abilities (e.g., social skills, learning skills, self-help skills, communication skills, etc.). The cognitive disability is also known as intellectual disability. These disabilities of cognition can slow down the learning process as well as the developing process of a child than a normal child. Cognitive disabilities can be caused by a brain abnormality, genetic disorder, illness (e.g., meningitis), or an external insult (e.g., automobile accident). These disabilities of cognition can be assessed through administration of standardized intelligence and adaptive behavior tests.

Two professional associations in the United States, i.e., the American Psychiatric Association (APA) and the American Association on Intellectual and

Developmental Disabilities (AAIDD), have each developed their own diagnostic criteria for intellectual disabilities (ID) and in this paper, the term cognitive disability is used interchangeably with ID. Each of their diagnostic criteria protocol has its own merits.

The American Psychiatric Association's (APA) diagnostic criteria for intellectual disability (ID), used to be known as mental retardation (MR), can be found in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5; APA, 2013). A summary of the diagnostic criteria in DSM-5 are as follows:

(1) Deficits in intellectual functioning and it includes various mental abilities, i.e., abstract thinking, academic learning (i.e., the ability to learn in class/school via traditional pedagogy), experiential learning (i.e., the ability to learn through experience, trial-and-error, and observation), judgment, planning, problem-solving, reasoning. These mental abilities can be assessed by administering IQ tests. According to the DSM-5 (APA, 2013), approximately two standard deviations below the average IQ score (within the range of standard scores from 90 to 109) represents a significant cognitive deficit or disability. Such an IQ score is typically at 70 or below. Generally, such IQ scores occur about 2.5% of the population. In other words, 97.5% of individuals of the same chronological age and culture would score higher. It is important to note that IQ the tests being administered must be standardized and culturally appropriate.

(2) Deficits/impairments in adaptive functioning and it includes skills required for an independent living and ability to perform appropriately and responsibly in activities of daily living (e.g., dressing, feeding and toileting). With limited abilities in these daily life skills, an individual will experience challenges that make it difficult to achieve age-appropriate standards of adaptive behavior. Without these skills, the person needs additional supports to succeed at home, school, or workplace. Functioning deficits in adaptive behavior can be assessed by administering standardized, culturally appropriate tests such as Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scales-Third Edition (VABS-3; Sparrow, Cicchetti, & Saulnier, 2016) and Diagnostic Adaptive Behavior Scale (DABS; Tassé et al., 2012, 2017). Various adaptive behavioral skills that are needed for daily living are as follows:

- a) Communication, which refers to the ability to convey information through words and actions from one person to another, and it also requires the ability to understand others as well as to express one's self through words or actions;
- b) Social skills that are critical for success in life, and they refer to the ability to interact effectively with others. Such skills include

- understanding and compliance with social rules, customs, and standards of public behavior, and they require a person's ability to process figurative/metaphorical expressions as well as to detect unspoken cues (e.g., body language, facial expressions, and hand gestures);
- c) Personal independence at home or outside, and such skills refer to one's self-care ability, e.g., bathing, dressing, and feeding. It also includes the ability to safely complete day-to-day tasks without guidance, e.g., cooking, cleaning, and laundry. Other routine activities performed in the community include grocery shopping and accessing public transportation.
 - d) School or workplace functioning, which refers to one's ability to conform to the social standards in class/school or at workplace. This includes one's ability to acquire new content knowledge, skills, and abilities. In addition, this acquired information needs to be applied by the person in a practical, adaptive manner, without excessive supervision, direction or guidance.
- a) Conceptual skills: These include language and literacy skills, concepts such as money, time, and number concepts, and self-direction.
 - b) Social skills: They are interpersonal skills which include social responsibility, self-esteem, gullibility, naïveté (i.e., wariness), social problem solving, and the ability to follow rules or obey laws, and to avoid being victimized.
 - c) Practical skills: They refer to activities of daily living (i.e., personal care), occupational skills, healthcare, travel or transportation, schedules/routines, safety, use of money, use of the telephone.

Standardized tests such as VABS-3 (Sparrow, Cicchetti, & Saulnier, 2016) and DABS (Tassé et al., 2012, 2017) mentioned earlier can be administered to determine limitations in an individual's adaptive behavior.

(3) Age of Onset: The condition of CogD or ID must originate during the developmental period, and this is defined to take place before the age of 22 years old. "Intellectual disability is one of several conditions known collectively as developmental disabilities" (AAIDD, 2022, para. 5).

(3) All these limitations happen during the developmental period of an individual. In other words, problems with intellectual or adaptive functioning should be evident during childhood or adolescence. If such problems began after this developmental period, the correct diagnosis would be neuro-cognitive disorder (e.g., a traumatic brain injury sustained from a car accident).

According to the AAIDD (see Schalock, Luckasson, & Tassé, 2021, for detail) cognitive disability (CogD) or intellectual disability (ID) is defined as "a condition characterized by significant limitations in both intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior that originates before the age of 22" (AAIDD, 2022, para. 1). The criteria for diagnostic identification of CogD or ID are as follows (AAIDD, 2022, para. 2-5):

(1) Intellectual Functioning (also known as intelligence) refers to "general mental capacity such as learning, reasoning, problem solving, and so on. To measure intellectual functioning, an IQ test is required, and, generally, the IQ score is "around 70 or as high as 75 to indicate a significant limitation in intellectual functioning" (AAIDD, 2022, para. 3).

(2) Adaptive Behavior, which is refers to as a "collection of conceptual, social, and practical skills that are learned and performed by people in their everyday lives" (AAIDD, 2022, para. 4). There are three subdomains in the adaptive behavior and they are as follows (AAIDD, 2022, para. 4.1-4.3):

The AAIDD (2022) also stresses additional factors, such as community environment typical of the individual's peers, linguistic diversity and cultural differences in the way people communicate, move and behave, to be considered when assessing ID. Finally, assessments of ID must also assume that "limitations often coexist with strengths in an individual, and that the individual's level of life functioning will improve if appropriate, personalized supports are provided over a sustained period" (AAIDD, 2022, para. 9).

Cognitive Disabilities: Developmental & Neurological

Cognitive disabilities (CogDs for short) are also known as disabilities of cognition. As mentioned earlier, based on the WHO (1980) definition for the term *disability*, it refers to any lack, limitation or restriction (that can be the result of an impairment) of one's ability to perform an activity in the manner or within the range considered normal for a typically developed individual. In the context of *cognitive disability* (also known as *intellectual disability* as defined by APA and AAIDD discussed earlier, it is used to refer to the condition of an individual who manifests some specific limitations in his/her mental functions and abilities (e.g., social skills and learning). These CogDs hamper the process of learning, slowing it down as well as interfering with the developing process of an individual. There may be overlapping in defining a developmental and cognitive disability. That is also why the term *intellectual and developmental disabilities* (IDD) is

often used to refer to the same challenging condition. The terms are broad labels that do not indicate the level of ability or skills. Hence, in short, CogD is a nebulous term that describes someone who has more than average difficulty performing cognitive tasks. CogDs are also considered as the most common disability type among the school-age children.

According to Chia (2010), CogDs can be further categorized under four sub-types of challenging issues - lexikos (literacy and language), calculatos (numeracy and mathematics), praxis (motor planning, coordination and execution), and gnosis (knowledge of self and the environment needed for adaptation and survival) - that impact on cognitive abilities (i.e., academic skills - traits and strategies that help an individual become a better learner - are essential for school success), which, in turn, interfere with the neuropsychological processes (i.e., psychological processes in the brain that are associated with the biological process, involving psychological, physiological and biological domains) involved in learning activities, and also the ability of relating to oneself (i.e., self-awareness and self-agency) as well as one’s immediate environment. The Figure 1 below shows the relationship among the three key factors: (i) cognitive abilities, (ii) neuropsychological processes, and (iii) academic skills.

Figure 1. Cognitive Disabilities: Deficits in Cognitive Abilities, Neuropsychological Processes and Academic Skills

The CogDs in each of these subcategories can result in a spectrum of disabilities that fall within either developmental disabilities (DDs) or neurological disabilities (NDs) (see Table 1 below). DDs consists of a diverse group of chronic conditions due to mental or physical impairments whose onset takes place before adulthood. People with DDs experience many difficulties in their lives such as “impairment in physical, learning, language, or behavior areas” (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention/CDC, 2022, para. 1). In the United States alone, “about one in six children in the U.S. have one or more developmental disabilities or other developmental delays” (CDC, 2022, para. 1). Though persist throughout an individual’s lifespan development,

DDs can be detected early with appropriate standardized assessment tools such as IQ tests and development screeners. If DD affects two or more areas of a child's development, the condition is often referred to as global developmental delay with the diagnostic code of EI-DD (if it is detected earlier between birth and 3 years of age) or PS-DD (if detected between 4 and 6 years of age) according to the Educator’s Diagnostic Manual (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2007).

Table 1. Subcategories of Cognitive Disabilities

Category	Developmental Disabilities	Neurological Disabilities
Lexikos (<i>Literacy & language</i>)	Dyslexia	Alexia
Calculatos (<i>Numeracy & mathematics</i>)	Dyscalculia	Acalculia
Praxis (<i>Motor planning, coordination & execution</i>)	Dyspraxia	Apraxia
Gnosis (<i>Knowledge of self & environment</i>)	Dysgnosia	Agnosia

Figure 2 shows a diagrammatic representation of all the developmental and neurological disabilities of cognition or CogDs.

Figure 2: Four Subcategories of Cognitive Disabilities

In this paper, the author has chosen to describe each of these four subcategories of CogDs by relating them to the Cattell-Horn-Carroll (CHC) framework of broad and narrow abilities, whose history of development can be traced back to the early 1940s when Cattell proposed his original conceptualization of intelligence (Flanagan, Ortiz, & Alfonso, 2013) based on the dichotomous understanding of cognitive ability referred to as fluid-crystallized theory or Gf-Gc theory. On one hand, the Gf is fluid intelligence that includes inductive and deductive reasoning abilities, which, in turn, are “influenced by biological and neurological factors as well as incidental learning through interaction with the environment” (Flanagan, Ortiz, & Alfonso, 2013, p. 7). On the other hand, the Gc refers to crystallized intelligence that generally consists of abilities related to acquired

knowledge, which, in turn, is very much influenced by acculturation (Cattell, 1957, 1971).

The CHC framework of human potential (or cognitive abilities) is more than just Gf-Gc theory. In 1965, John Horn, a student of Raymond B. Cattell (b.1905-d.1998) (cited in Flanagan, Ortiz, & Alfonso, 2013) expanded the dichotomous model to include four more abilities: i.e., Gv which is visual perception or processing; Gsm which is short-term acquisition and retrieval; Glr which is long-term storage and retrieval; and Gs which concerns the speed of processing. Later, Horn (1967) added Ga, which is auditory processing ability, to the Gf-Gc

model and refined the definitions of Gv, Gs and Glr (Horn & Stankov, 1982).

In 1991, Horn added Gt which represents an individual's quickness in responding (reaction time) and decision-making (decision speed). Finally, Gq which is the quantitative ability and Grw which represents the broad reading/writing ability were also added by Horn (1991) and Woodcock (1994), respectively. The Gf-Gc theory expanded to a 10-factor model: Gf, Gc, Gv, Gsm, Glr, Gs, Ga, Gt, Gq and Grw in that sequence (see Table 2 for a summary of the 10 broad abilities; also see Flanagan, Ortiz, & Alfonso, 2013, for detail).

Table 2. 10 CHC-based Broad Abilities

Broad Ability	What is it?	What does it concern? (Flanagan, Ortiz, & Alfonso, 2013, p. 17)
Gf	Fluid intelligence	The deliberate but flexible control of attention to solve novel, on-the-spot problems that cannot be performed by relying exclusively on previously learned habits, schema, & scripts
Gc	Crystallized intelligence	The depth & breadth of knowledge & skills valued by one's culture
Gv	Visual processing	The ability to make use of stimulated mental imagery (often in conjunction with currently perceived images) to solve problems
Gsm	Short-term memory	The ability to encode, maintain, & manipulate information in one's immediate awareness
Glr	Long-term storage & retrieval	The ability to store, consolidate, & retrieve information over periods of time measured in minutes, hours, days, & years
Gs	Processing speed	The ability to perform simple, repetitive cognitive tasks quickly & fluently
Ga	Auditory processing	The ability to detect & process meaningful nonverbal information in sound
Gt	Reaction & decision speed	The speed of making very simple decisions or judgments when items are presented one at a time
Gq	Quantitative knowledge	The depth & breadth of knowledge related to mathematics
Grw	Reading & writing	The depth & breadth of knowledge & skills related to written language

Cognitive Abilities #1: Lexikos - Abilities & Skills in Literacy & Language

There are two key specific learning disabilities that are concerned about literacy and language. The first one is the disability of reading known as dyslexia, while the second one is the disability of writing known as dysgraphia. In some ways, both are related to each other in terms of literacy process and product (see Chia, 2007, for detail).

Dyslexia is "a specific learning disability that is neurobiological in origin. It is characterized by difficulties with accurate and/or fluent word recognition and by poor spelling and decoding abilities. These difficulties typically result from a deficit in the phonological component of language that is often unexpected in relation to other cognitive abilities and the provision of effective classroom instruction. Secondary consequences may include problems in reading comprehension and reduced reading experience that can impede growth of vocabulary and background knowledge" (Lyon, Shaywitz, & Shaywitz, 2003, p. 2). People with brain lesions have been found to have difficulties in literacy and language processing and this condition is known as alexia (see Friedman, Ween, & Albert, 1993, for detail).

CHC broad abilities for reading include Ga, Gc, Glr, Grw, Gs, Gsm, Gt¹ (see Table 2 for description; also see Flanagan, Ortiz, & Alfonso, 2013, for more detail).

There is another specific learning disability to do with deficits in writing deficits, and it is known as dysgraphia. Berninger (2020) has defined dysgraphia as "a specific learning disability that affects how easily children acquire written language and how well they use written language to express their thoughts ... [d]ysgraphia is the condition of impaired letter writing by hand, that is, disabled handwriting and sometimes spelling. Impaired handwriting can interfere with learning to spell words in writing ... Dysgraphia may occur alone or with dyslexia (impaired reading disability) or with oral and written language learning disability (OWL LD, also referred to as selective language impairment, SLI)" (p. 1). If writing problems are the result of neurological impairments, the condition is known as lexical or orthographic agraphia (Beauvois & Derouesne, 1981).

¹ Gt will be required for speed reading (first started by Evelyn Wood in 1959; cited in Frank, 1994).

CHC broad abilities for writing include Ga, Gc, Gf, Glr, Grw, Gs, Gsm, [Gt]², Gv (see Table 2 for description; also see Flanagan, Ortiz, & Alfonso, 2013, for more detail).

Cognitive Abilities#2: Calculators - Abilities & Skills in Numeracy & Mathematics

Dyscalculia concerns poor number sense and faulty skill in subitizing (i.e., “instantly seeing how many”) and it refers to difficulty learning or comprehending arithmetic, e.g., problems in understanding and manipulating numbers, difficulties in performing mathematical calculations and trouble in acquiring mathematical facts (Miller, 2021). It is often mistaken for what is known as math dyslexia, but such a term is misleading as dyslexia is a different condition from dyscalculia. Disabilities in learning mathematics can also be the result of some types of brain injury, and it is termed acalculia (Ardila & Rosselli, 2002) rather than called dyscalculia, which is of innate, genetic or developmental origin.

CHC broad abilities for numeracy and mathematics: Gc, Gf, Glr, Gq, Gs, Gsm, Gv, Gt³ (see Table 2 for description; also see Flanagan, Ortiz, & Alfonso, 2013, for more detail).

Cognitive Abilities#3: Praxis - Abilities & Skills in Motor Planning, Coordination & Execution

“Developmental coordination disorder (DCD), also known as ... developmental dyspraxia or simply dyspraxia, is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by impaired coordination of physical movements as a result of brain messages not being accurately transmitted to the body” (Wikipedia contributors, 2022, para. 1). Interestingly, praxis has also to do with phenomenal will, also known as self-agency, which is the sense that actions are self-generated (Libet, 1985; Libet et al., 1983). Wegner (2003, 2004) later defined the three criteria of self-agency: (i) priority, (ii) exclusivity, and (iii) consistency. According to Wegner (2003, 2004), priority refers to a planned action before its initiation. Between the initiated action and the subsequent effect is that time interval known as the intentional binding. Next, exclusivity refers to the effect due to an individual's action instead of other potential causes for the effect. Lastly, consistency refers to one's planned action that must happen as intended. It is not within the scope of this paper to discuss the topic in-depth.

Deficits are noted in fine or gross motor skills movements in an individual with DCD and they interfere with activities of daily living. Often

described as the disorder in skill acquisition, learning as well as execution of coordinated motor skills, when assessed, is found to be substantially below that expected of the individual's chronological age. Difficulties in dyspraxia include clumsiness, slowness and inaccuracy of performance of motor skills (e.g., untidy handwriting which is also described as cacographia, clumsy in handling cutlery or using tools). DCD or dyspraxia is also accompanied by challenges in organizing, paying attention, time management, and working memory. Problems in motor-related activities due to brain injuries are often identified as apraxia (see De Renzi & Faglioni, 2020; Heilman, Watson, & Gonzalez-Rothi, 2007 for more detail).

The authors have selectively included the following CHC broad abilities, which they believe are related to movement and coordination: Gp, Gs, Gsm, Gv, Gt (see Table 2 for description; also see Flanagan, Ortiz, & Alfonso, 2013, for more detail).

Cognitive Abilities#4: Gnosis - Abilities & Skills in Knowledge Acquisition

Dysgnosis is rarely mentioned in literature and it refers to any intellectual impairment. It is a cognitive disorder relating to any mental illness. Though very little is written about it, the term comes from the Greek word *gnosis* which means “knowledge.” Best known for its implication within the Gnosticism, i.e., “collection of religious ideas and systems which coalesced in the late 1st century AD among Jewish and early Christian sects” (Margis, 2005, p. 3515), the term *gnosis* signifies “a spiritual knowledge of insight into humanity's real nature as divine, leading to the deliverance of the divine spark within humanity from the constraints of earthly existence” (Rudolph, 2001, p. 2; also see Brakke, 2010; Ehrman, 2003; May, 2008, for more detail). The authors of this paper chose to define dysgnosis as a form of cognitive impairment in two aspects of knowledge: (i) The first aspect concerns the knowledge of self (i.e., self-awareness or being mindful of oneself and one's actions) and that includes self-activated tasks, especially in self-agency (also known as the phenomenal will), which is the sense that actions are self-generated (also see Wegner, 2003, 2004); and (ii) The second aspect concerns the knowledge of one's surrounding or context, in which one's action, utterance, or expression can only be understood relative to that context (Price, 2008). This may also include epistemic contextualism (EC), whose view concerns what is expressed by a knowledge attribution (i.e., a claim to the effect that *S* “knows” that *p*) that depends partly on something in the context of the attributor, and hence, what is known as the view of attributor contextualism. It is not within the scope of this paper to delve into this topic, but interested readers may want to read more about it elsewhere

² Gt is needed when participating in poetry slam (first started by Marc Smith in 1986), for example (see Aptowicz, 2009, for detail).

³ Gt is needed when participating in abacus, speed mathematics and speed calculation (Handley, 2012).

(e.g., Kompa, 2014; Price, 2008, as provided in the References below).

The American neuroscientist, Benjamin Libet (b.1916-d.2007), who was a pioneer in the field of human consciousness, was the first to study self-agency, discovering that brain activity predicts the action before one even has conscious awareness of his or her intention to act upon that action (Libet, 1985; Libet et al., 1983). This is the knowledge of self as described by the authors of this paper. Interestingly, in the field of psychology and neuroscience, there is another intriguing concept based on the hypothesis of an American psychologist and psychohistorian, Julian Jaynes (b.1920-d.1997), arguing that the human mind used to operate in a way that cognitive functions in the brain were divided between that *which speaks* and that *which listens and obeys*. Jaynes (1976) termed it the *bicameral mind*, from which his hypothesis of bicameral mentality (or the sense of bicamerality of the unconscious mind) came about. He argued that the evolutionary breakdown of this division gave rise to human consciousness. Jaynes (1976) also pointed out that bicameral mentality was the normal and ubiquitous state of the human mind as recently as 3,000 years ago, near the end of the Mediterranean Bronze Age (approximately from 3300BC to 1200BC). If this were indeed the case, there is more to it than meets the eye, concerning the knowledge of self, one's existence, and relationship with one's context. Our understanding of gnosis and also of agnosis (i.e., ignorance) should go beyond what is currently presented here.

If the condition of knowledge acquisition deficits is a result of some form of brain injury, it is known as agnosia, which is the inability to process sensory information, i.e., it includes severe to profound mental retardation (see Farah, 1992, for detail). It is important not to confuse between the two terms: agnosis and agnosia. The former refers to ignorance while the latter is a serious disability. Often there is a loss of ability to recognize objects (Konen et al., 2011), persons (Damasio, Tranel, & Damasio, 1990), sounds (Shell, 2015), shapes (Milner et al., 1991), or smells (Pryse-Phillips, 1975) while the specific sense is not defective nor is there any significant memory loss.

The authors have selectively included the following CHC broad abilities, which they believe are closely related to knowledge acquisition: Ga, Gf, Gkn, Glr, Gq, Grw, Gsm, Gt (see Table 2 for description; also see Flanagan, Ortiz, & Alfonso, 2013, for more detail).

Conclusion

There remains an infinite realm of unknowable unknowns in our pursuit of knowledge in the area of

cognitive disabilities and their subcategories within the CHC theory of broad abilities (and also narrow abilities, which are not covered in this paper). While much has already been researched, written and published on the first three subcategories of cognitive abilities covering the developmental and neurological domains of lexikos, calculatos and praxis, very little is done on gnosis which begs to be thoroughly investigated and further studies are needed.

The authors hope that this paper would capture the interest of readers to find out more on related topics pertaining to cognitive disabilities, and also to motivate others to pick up their pen or laptop to write papers and/or share what they know or other interesting ideas and thoughts relevant to cognitive abilities, disabilities and other unknowable unknowns in the field of cognitive science.

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